

Online Educational Resources Library

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Reprohealth and gender

TITLE	LINK	TYPE OF RESOURCE	AUTORSHIP	LICENCE	LANGUAGE
Female reproductive system	http://bit.ly/3rZjMD1	Image	Self-authorship	Creative Commons	Spanish
Female reproductive system (blank)	https://bit.ly/3QaD7cq	Image	created by others	Creative Commons	
Henry Ford Hospital by Frida Kalho	https://bit.ly/46X8EW8	Image	created by others	Creative Commons	
Fertilisation phases of a human egg cell	https://bit.ly/45MfmwT	Image	created by others	Creative Commons	English
Frida Kahlo: The woman behind the legend - Iseult Gillespie	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=B9XYtPqWLB4	Video	created by others	Creative Commons	English
Female infertility	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/181AGYuileuhZLukpFHkRCfAdX4OEVA4Z/edit#gid=1331091799	Video	created by others	Other	English
Female infertility	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/181AGYuileuhZLukpFHkRCfAdX4OEVA4Z/edit#gid=524837384	Video	created by others	Other	English
Female infertility	https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/181AGYuileuhZLukpFHkRCfAdX4OEVA4Z/edit#gid=390589056	Video	created by others	Other	English
Biology video rubric	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1xdvXhV-BkzGBxkKZKYzx6L7dDJux0bSe/view?usp=drive_link	PDF	Self-authorship	Other	English

Rúbrica del vídeo de Biología	https://drive.google.com/file/d/1eVFjhjKzD9IkTW1ccm6Oe3Qk33-LK2o/view?usp=drive_link	PDF	Self-authorship	Copyright	Spanish
Human embryos under the microscope	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=J99mZSQtOms&t=75s	Video	created by others	Copyright	English
Reproduction Quiz game	https://wordwall.net/es/resource/53950562/ciencias-naturales/reproduction	Interactive resource	created by others	Other	English
Female reproductive system	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Female_reproductive_system#/media/File:Blausen_0400_FemaleReproSystem_02.png	Image	created by others	Creative Commons	English
Female reproductive system	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BlxLwLGTM5l	Video	created by others	Copyright	Spanish
Female reproductive system	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a8fgm-zEYjQ	Video	created by others	Copyright	English
Male reproductive system picture	https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/7/71/Male_anatomy_es.svg	Image	created by others	Creative Commons	Spanish
Male reproductive system picture	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Male_reproductive_system#/media/File:Male_anatomy_en.svg	Image	created by others	Creative Commons	English
Male reproductive system video	https://youtu.be/pzSUy38aHus?si=qgFAZFijZx7-z-8E	Video	created by others	Other	Spanish
Male reproductive system video	https://youtu.be/Vxwyp3EH4L8?si=a4Esv3zMNmcJD73b	Video	created by others	Other	English
Cervix 3D printed	https://www.abc.es/familia/bebes/abci-logran-padres-gracias-protesis-unica-impresa-202012152119_noticia.html	Other	created by others	Other	Spanish

prosthesis article					
3D scanning characteristics article	https://www.asorcad.es/blog/escaneado-3d-caracteristicas-y-beneficios-de-su-uso/	Other	created by others	Other	Spanish
Reproductive System	https://quizlet.com/it/852430229/apparato-riproduttore-flash-cards/?i=1zespi&x=1jqU	Interactive resource	Self-authorship	Other	Italian

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